

1 **CDK4 is activated in human glioblastoma.**

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6 We report here the identification of CDK4 as a viable therapeutic target in human glioblastoma. CDK4
7 was retrieved as an up-regulated and differentially expressed kinase using whole transcriptome technology that
8 measures and compares total transcription in normal brain tissue and the glioblastoma brain tumor. While
9 survival data from humans with glioblastoma is not available to us at this time, we recently described elsewhere
10 a strong and statistically significant correlation between low CDK4 tumor expression and enhanced human
11 survival in humans with breast cancer: with lower CDK4 expression levels, and thus lower CDK4 catalytic
12 function, significantly associating with enhanced overall survival (increased lifetime following diagnosis).
13 Here, we establish a paradigm in solid tumor biology: that CDK4 is a frequently up-regulated and differentially
14 expressed solid tumor vulnerability in humans with cancer, and that low CDK4 expression in the solid tumor,
15 and thus low CDK4 activity, just as one experiences following administration of a CDK4/6 inhibitor, is likely to
16 confer superior overall survival in the solid tumor patient if the tumor expresses relatively high quantities of
17 this cell division-promoting kinase. Together, we argue and thus demonstrate using whole transcriptome
18 technologies and human survival data in multiple human solid tumor cohorts, in hundreds of patients with
19 cancer of the breast and the stomach, that CDK4 pharmacologic inhibition is a viable therapeutic strategy in
20 humans with the brain cancer glioblastoma who currently possess limited therapeutic options, whose tumors
21 contain relatively large quantities of a viable therapeutic target (the cyclin dependent kinase *CDK4*), of which a
22 family of small molecule inhibitors, the -ciclibs, is readily available.
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1 Figure 1: Glioblastomas, in human, express relatively high quantities of CDK4. It is differentially expressed
 2 and up-regulated.

Probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
202246_s_at	4.11E-17	-9.68922	28.0959999	-0.87295629	CDK4	3857/47229	91.8

6 Figure 2: The tumors of humans with gastric cancer (cancer of the stomach) also express relatively high
 7 quantities of CDK4. CDK4 is differentially expressed and up-regulated in human gastric cancer.

Probe ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
202246_s_at	4.11E-17	-9.68922	28.0959999	-0.87295629	CDK4	4095/54675	92.5

11 Figure 3: In gastric cancer, just as in human breast cancer, low CDK4 expression correlates with superior
 12 overall survival: decreased CDK4 tumor expression, just as one manifests during administration of a CDK4/6
 13 inhibitor, confers increased lifetime to the gastric cancer patient.

22 Low tumor expression of CDK4: 31.33 months

23 High tumor expression of CDK4: 22.2 months